

**МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА**

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Том 2, Выпуск 9, 30 Сентябрь

**MODEL OF THE TEACHING PROCESS OF INFORMATICS AND
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES ON THE BASIS OF AN INNOVATIVE
APPROACH, IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS .**

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***Abstract:** Today, the term "design" is widely used in pedagogical literature and practice. It is connected with the development of specific lessons, individual subjects, integrated educational subjects, educational activities or complexes of subjects and helps to create technological pedagogical objects, including pedagogical processes. Based on the designed pedagogical processes, there are ideas that gradually lead to a positive result based on the laws of formation of professional qualities of the individual.*

***Key words :** traditional educational technologies, information competence, intellectual abilities, critical thinking, rebus, crosswords.*

**MODEL PROCESS OBUCHENIYA INFORMATICE AND
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND BASED INNOVATION,
MECHANISM REALIZATION**

***Abstract.** The current term "design" is widely used in pedagogical literature and practice. It is related to the development of concrete lessons, special subjects, integrated educational subjects, educational details and complex subjects, and enables creative and technological pedagogical objects and a whole number of pedagogical processes. V osnove sproektirovannyx pedagogicheskix procesov vznikayut idei, kotorye privodyat k pojitelnomu resultu, osnonomu na zakonomernostyakh formovaniya professionalnyx kachestv lichnosti .*

***Key words:** traditional educational technologies, information competence, intellectual abilities, critical thinking, puzzles, crosswords.*

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Abstract . Today, the term "design" is widely used in pedagogical literature and practice. Design is connected with the development of specific lessons, individual subjects, integrated academic subjects, educational activities or complexes of subjects and helps to create technological pedagogical objects, including pedagogical processes. Based on the designed pedagogical processes, there are ideas that gradually lead to a positive result based on the laws of formation of professional qualities of a person..

Keywords : traditional educational technologies, information competence, intellectual abilities, critical thinking, puzzles, crossword puzzles.

Sign in . Today's in the day problematic teaching , mental actions step by step formation , education of giving computer technology , module education technology , etc wide is being used and they are pedagogical the process to design basis will be

Pedagogical design pedagogue and of students efficient activities work exit with depend Thorough , literate designed pedagogical processes , technologies and another objects by means of pedagogue student identity and self to develop achieves , various negative factors effect reduces With that pedagogue individual development of the student to himself special the project creates Education process improvement efficiency in increasing theory leader place is occupying

Lesson official education of the field primary basis , continuous education of the process organize doer brick , teacher and of pedagogues activity show place as follows structural from parts consists of :

1. Reader or students
2. Teacher or pedagogue .
3. Teaching technical tools .
4. In class need to be normative documents (program , training plan , calendar plan , textbook , methodology manuals , lessons development) .
5. Method and styles .

Lesson criteria in determining to the following attention to give need :

Education purpose , from him pending results , education giver and recipients , education content , method , form , means , control and evaluation .

Education process - education giver with education receiver between known goals based on defined knowledge and skills content to find directed process considered his purpose education result as student reach must has been knowledge ,

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skill and personal qualities determines

Traditional lesson shape save the rest without lesson of the process reasonable organize ethylis

hi teacher by of students interests gain their education in the process activity constant encouraged training , education topic little by little into pieces being their content opening " Debate ", " Mental attack ”, “ Small in groups performance ", " Rolly game ” methods application , colorful interesting examples brought to the students practical exercises independent to perform encouragement , different evaluation methods and education of means in place and own in time use is required .

Unconventional the lesson transition in the process main attention student to the person is focused and this is in real life and in society face giving event and of processes condensed and simplified appearance in the classroom create and in them of students personally participation and activity in return education to get in the eye holder method is considered

To the child so thing to give it should be that nothing today , now to live not possible and that's it that he knows always , long from years and then again and again look let him throw it . So circumstances it will be a lesson during appropriate-inappropriate respectively many method and methods by laying thrown away Teaching methods choose teacher in class solution to do intended depending on the issue will be For example , new the material statement in reaching one different methods if used , it in strengthening second and the subject in generalization again another methods is used .

of the lesson different stages thorough to think and efficient methods apply very important Teacher of the lesson the most 4-5 minutes at the beginning common to ask done increases and of students which group past lesson according to enough level that he has not mastered determines and next in asking of the class attention the most this is it first to the matter looks

First , to the questions in detail answer give will receive from students asks . As a result of the class one part for complexity The material made is understandable will be This is the method of students in training defects notice and that's it immediately eliminate in reaching help gives This is it of the method efficiency is also the same then Although each of the pedagogue at work quite a bit method and styles there is though , them from applying expected goal of the pupil educational

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their work from activation consists of Teacher's task efficient of methods using , in students activity qualities content find and difficulties to overcome is to teach . That's a lot important in students being taught to science was , from him while practical to the activity turns and teaching of the process work makes it easier .

Games different to goals directed will be They are didactic , educational , activity developing and socialization purposes is used . Play didactic purpose knowledge scope , know activity , practical in the activity knowledge , skill and skills application , general education qualification and skills development , work skills development to expand directed will be Play educational purpose independence , will education , certain approaches , point of view views , spiritual , aesthetic worldview in formation cooperation , collectivism , team ability to enter and leave , communicativeness to educate directed will be Didactic principles account received without , to students not only of facts strictly scientific statement give maybe of teaching different interesting using methods it is necessary For example , to many known and popular has been crossword game in students interest education it is natural . Encyclopedia in the dictionary as defined , his the term English " cross " - crossed , " ward " - word said meaning that is , for the first time in the 20th century in their heads discover done Time pass with his types multiply , chainword , chaincrossword , crosschainword , rotation crossword , diagonal crosswords thinking found Each of them in the form of words location and connection with difference does Crossword in the form of request shape students for always interesting and to himself pulling is a method .

To many known and popular has been crossword game in students interest wake up it is natural . Crossword in the form of request shape students for always interesting and to himself pulling is a method . This to the game students that's it level entering they go , even themselves information communication technologies of different topics according to crosswords make up can Independent creative of activity such shape useful to be with together , only knowledgeable students only not only low absorbers takes Other study poor assimilator of subjects students most of the time information communication better than technologies and diligent to students they become Crosswords simple to be with together , famous scientists , scholars to the names , to the subject exactly suitable coming special to terms attention attraction of reaching efficient tool is also

Conclusion . of the lesson different stages thorough to think and efficient methods apply very important Teacher of the lesson the most 4-5 minutes at the

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